

Up-converted photorefractive optical transient detection with femtosecond laser pulses

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Abstract: We report on experimental demonstration of optical transient detection (OTD) based on photorefractive two-wave mixing of femtosecond pulses. The demonstrated technique also combines nonlinear-crystal-based OTD with up-conversion from infrared into the visible range. The approach enables measurement of phase changes of a dynamic signal in the infrared using GaP- or Si-based detectors while suppressing stationary background. Experimental results reveal existence of the relation between input phases in the infrared and output phases in the visible wavelength range. We further present experimental evidence of additional merits of up-converted transient phase analysis under noisy conditions, such as residual continuous-wave emission affecting the ultrashort pulses from the laser.

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1. Introduction

Two-wave mixing (TWM) in photorefractive crystals offers an attractive approach to interferometry for optical detection of phase changes with background suppression, owing to spatial and temporal adaptability. Background suppression greatly improves the contrast, thereby enhancing visualization, intensity, and phase information. In photorefractive-based interferometers, a dynamic index grating is created in the crystal by means of the TWM light interference pattern, where the interfering signal and pump beams also transmit and diffract from the index grating, achieving beam coupling [1–3]. Thus, it can function as an adaptive interferometer [4,5], where the grating adapts to the relatively slow and undesirable variation in beam wave front caused by external perturbations such as temperature or air fluctuations, ensuring continuous compensation. Nevertheless, fast phase variations cannot be followed by the grating, giving rise to the conversion of input phase changes to output intensity modulation.

In particular, a TWM process can be set for background suppression and photorefractive optical transient detection (OTD). This has been implemented in imaging systems for transient detection imaging (TDI), a type of system also named optical novelty filters. TDI systems based on photorefractive TWM were demonstrated by Cronin-Golomb et al. [6], and subsequently analyzed theoretically by Anderson and Feinberg [7]. Optical novelty filters have been implemented for many applications including transient detection microscopy [8], particle velocimetry [9], microfluidic dynamics [10], as well as measurement of phase changes introduced by moving objects [11–13]. Moreover, measurements in imaging devices of the transient output phase and

its relation to input phase changes have recently been reported for the first time using off-axis interferometry [14]. However, previous works have deployed continuous-wave (cw) lasers for OTD, and the use of ultrashort pulses has so far remained unexplored. While coherent ultrafast laser sources providing high-repetition-rate femtosecond (fs) pulses in the infrared (IR) are in great demand for a variety of applications including material characterization, molecular spectroscopy [15], trace gas sensing [16] and reflectometry through turbid media [17], their use in OTD will significantly enhance performance, enabling deployment of alternate infrared photorefractive materials such as semiconductors which exhibit faster response times [18,19], with applications in vibronics [20–24] and protein detection [25], among others.

In this proof-of-concept demonstration, we report OTD in single-spot photodetector using IR femtosecond pulses from a mode-locked Ti:sapphire laser. The high peak power of the ultrashort femtosecond pulses further enables up-conversion detection of output transient signals in the visible through second harmonic generation (SHG), for the first time. Moreover, we investigate the OTD output phase in the visible and its relation to the input signal phase changes in the IR. The implementation of up-conversion detection opens new avenues for exploring infrared transient signal detection and analysis using semiconductor materials in combination with infrared laser, while taking advantage of the fast and low-noise off-the-shelf detectors in the visible. It should be noted that while here we demonstrate up-conversion in a photodetector, this could be extended to imaging where up-conversion sensing based on sum-frequency mixing (SFM) or SHG is well-known as a practical solution to circumvent some limitations of IR image sensors such as signal-to-noise ratio, speed, resolution, or cooling needs in some demanding applications [26–30].

Several demonstrations have been reported based on the OTD concept, but mostly in the visible range and using cw lasers. Demonstration of refractive index grating formation by TWM using ultrashort pulses has been reported for signal amplification in some photorefractive materials such as BaTiO₃ and Sn₂P₂S₆ [31–37]. However, signal suppression and phase detection using optical transient up-conversion detection has not been previously demonstrated.

2. Theoretical background

When two beams interfere at an angle inside a photorefractive crystal, beam coupling occurs because a refractive index grating (a dynamic volume hologram) is generated that automatically fulfills the Bragg condition. The grating is formed via linear electrooptic (Pockels) effect in response to the creation of a space-charge electric field, which results from charge migration from bright regions to dark regions following photoexcitation by the intensity interference pattern. By default, the grating is shifted from the intensity pattern by $\pi/2$ (diffusion-dominated charge transport) in a direction that depends on the orientation of the crystal polar axis (c^+ -axis) relative to the interference pattern. This shift, which can be modified by applying an external dc electric field (drift-driven recording), is responsible for the asymmetric energy transfer existing between beams. Therefore, one beam is attenuated and the other is amplified.

The photorefractive response time strongly depends on the material [1,12,38,39], ranging from seconds to microseconds, and this inertia is essential for OTD, as we explain below. Suppose that an equilibrium is reached where the output signal is suppressed or is highly attenuated. If now the input signal beam abruptly changes, while the refractive index grating remains steady, the interferometric conditions change and the output signal also changes: in other words, the interferometer responds to signal changes. If the change is not reversed, the refractive index grating slowly evolves towards a new equilibrium in which the same signal suppression or attenuation state is recovered. The theory of OTD under full signal suppression is described in detail in [14]. In the experiments reported here, however, we have not reached full suppression but strong attenuation, up to 80% of the input signal intensity. Therefore, we must adapt the theory to the experimental conditions. Assume that, for some arbitrary input fields of complex

amplitudes, $\bar{A}_{1,2}^{\text{in}}$ (subscripts 1 and 2 denote the signal and the pump, respectively), a stationary grating is formed after a transient. We call this equilibrium situation the reference state, which we denote by an overbar. The effect of the reference volume hologram on any input fields, $A_{1,2}^{\text{in}}$, can be described by a transfer matrix of elements, \bar{T}_{ij} , so the output signal from the photorefractive crystal is given by [14]

$$A_1^{\text{out}} = \bar{T}_{11}A_1^{\text{in}} + \bar{T}_{12}A_2^{\text{in}}. \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) remains valid as long as the grating remains in the reference state, which occurs if the modification of the inputs from \bar{A}_i^{in} to A_i^{in} lasts for a short time compared with the photorefractive response time. Note that Eq. (1) is a linear input-output relation, meaning that the nonlinearity in the photorefractive effect occurs during the grating formation process but, once the equilibrium has been reached, the system behaves as a linear interferometer.

In [14] we assumed $\bar{A}_1^{\text{out}} = 0$, i.e. the signal output field is fully suppressed in the reference state. Here we let $\bar{A}_1^{\text{out}} \neq 0$, so there is a background signal intensity, $\bar{I}_1^{\text{out}} = |\bar{A}_1^{\text{out}}|^2$, which we denote by I^0 to simplify the notation. Let us apply Eq. (1) to the reference state, ($A_{1,2}^{\text{in}} = \bar{A}_{1,2}^{\text{in}}$), and also to another state in which the input signal phase has been shifted by $\Delta\varphi_1$ ($A_1^{\text{in}} = \bar{A}_1^{\text{in}}e^{i\Delta\varphi_1}$, $A_2^{\text{in}} = \bar{A}_2^{\text{in}}$), and subtract the corresponding output signal intensities so that

$$I^{\text{OTD}} \equiv I_1^{\text{out}} - I^0 = 2I^{\text{ref}}[\cos(\beta^{\text{ref}} + \Delta\varphi_1) - \cos(\beta^{\text{ref}})], \quad (2)$$

where $I^{\text{ref}} = |\bar{T}_{11}\bar{T}_{12}\bar{A}_1^{\text{in}}\bar{A}_2^{\text{in},*}|$ and $\beta^{\text{ref}} = \arg(\bar{T}_{11}\bar{T}_{12}\bar{A}_1^{\text{in}}\bar{A}_2^{\text{in},*})$ are the modulus and phase of an interterminal term corresponding to the reference state. Under perfect suppression ($\bar{A}_1^{\text{out}} = 0$), one has $\bar{T}_{12}\bar{A}_2^{\text{in}} = -\bar{T}_{11}\bar{A}_1^{\text{in}}$ trivially from Eq. (1), so $\beta^{\text{ref}} = \pi$, and $I^{\text{OTD}} = 2I^{\text{ref}}[1 - \cos(\Delta\varphi_1)]$, hence

$$I^{\text{OTD}} = 4I^{\text{ref}}\sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi_1}{2}\right), \quad (3)$$

which is the usual OTD signal under full signal suppression [11–14]. Fortunately, even when suppression is not perfect the phase β^{ref} is always π , at least for diffusion-dominated crystals, as will be reported elsewhere. Thus, we always have a transient output intensity given by Eq. (3). The coefficient, I^{ref} , is determined experimentally by means of a fit on the dependence between the output intensity and the signal phase shifts. This method is the basis of the conventional approach of inferring the input phase change from intensity measurements [11,12].

To conclude this Section, we mention that the theory presented above is strictly valid in principle for OTD under quasi-cw illumination conditions. Therefore, one should be cautious when applying Eq. (3) to experiments with mode-locked ultrafast lasers, since the physical processes involved in the photorefractive effect (photoionization, free-carrier recombination, diffusion, and drift [1]) have different characteristic time scales, and the corresponding relations with pulse duration and repetition rate may have consequences for the eventual establishment of a (dynamical) equilibrium and the nature of that equilibrium. The carrier recombination time, τ_R , is a primary time scale [33,40,41]. The pulse duration of mode-locked lasers (ps or sub-ps) is orders of magnitude shorter than the recombination time, τ_R (hundreds of ps to hundreds of ns), so in all practical cases mode-locked pulses act as Dirac-deltas on the photoionization events, preceded and followed by dark periods during which free charges migrate and recombine [40,41]. The duration of those dark periods is roughly the pulse period, T_p (in our case $T_p \cong 13$ ns), which we must compare with $\tau_R^{\text{BaTiO}_3} \cong 100$ ps [42] and $\tau_R^{\text{SBN}} > 500$ ns [43]. Thus, in BaTiO₃ case, $T_p \gg \tau_R$, so all carriers recombine before the next pulse arrives, while in the SBN case, $T_p \ll \tau_R$, so carriers relax little between successive pulses and the process is more similar to a quasi-cw situation. However, when the pulses are weak, each pulse produces a very small change in the system, and once an equilibrium has been reached the situation is similar to cw or quasi-cw and short-pulse illumination scenarios [43]. In particular, no enhancement of the photorefractive

response is observed under mode-locked pulse illumination unlike usual $\chi^{(2)}$ or $\chi^{(3)}$ processes based on instantaneous nonlinearities. To be more precise, by weak pulses we mean that their peak intensity is small enough to ignore two-photon absorption and their fluence is well below the saturation value [41]. Both requirements are safely satisfied in our experiments, since the beams illuminating the photorefractive crystals are not focused.

The main differences appear in the grating formation transient and diffraction efficiency [33,40,43]. A critical issue in pulsed experiments that is not present in cw illumination is the synchronous nature of pump and signal pulses, as they must overlap inside the crystal. Apart from the obvious decrease in the intensity interference pattern due to a relative delay between pump and signal pulses, other subtle effects can appear with chirped pulses (not our case), such as the addition of a phase to the diffracted pulse that depends quadratically on the relative delay between pulses [33,44]. Therefore, we conclude that the OTD theory under cw illumination is applicable to our experiments.

3. Experimental setup

The schematic of the experimental setup for the femtosecond up-converted OTD system is shown in Fig. 1. The pump source is a Kerr-lens mode-locked (KLM) Ti:sapphire laser (Coherent, Mira 900), providing up to 1.5 W of average power in ~ 130 fs pulses at 76 MHz repetition rate at 805 nm with a full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) spectral bandwidth of 7 nm. The laser beam is collimated using a telescope (L1 with $f' = 100$ mm, L2 with $f' = 50$ mm) resulting in a FWHM diameter of 2.4 mm and, using a half-wave plate (HWP), the polarization is adjusted to yield extraordinary (e) beam in the horizontal plane. The laser beam is split into a weak signal and a strong pump beam using a 10:90 beam-splitter (BS). Signal and pump optical attenuators (A) are used for control and optimization of pump/signal ratios.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup for femtosecond up-converted OTD. Signal and pump interact at the SBN (C1) and BaTiO₃ (C2) photorefractive crystals via TWM. The output signal is up-converted via SHG in a BIBO (C3) crystal. HWP: half-wave plate. BS: beam splitter. HR: high-reflector. HS: harmonic separator. PZT: piezo-mirror. A: attenuator. L1-L4: lenses. D1-D2: photodetectors. e-pol: extraordinary polarization (horizontal). o-pol: ordinary polarization (vertical).

The signal and pump beams intersect at the first nonlinear crystal (C1), a 0.01 wt % CeO₂-doped strontium barium niobate (SBN:61, given by Sr_xBa_(1-x)Nb₂O₆, where $x = 0.61$) photorefractive crystal (Altechna, aperture 5×5 mm², 5 mm). The output signal and pump beams from the first crystal then intersect at the second nonlinear crystal (C2), a barium titanate (BaTiO₃) photorefractive crystal (BAE Systems, aperture 5.23×6.67 mm², length 7 mm).

The c^+ -axes of both crystals are oriented in order to enable energy transfer from signal to pump under steady-state operation. We would like to mention that we use the available crystals in our lab at the time of the experiment, and further optimization using single crystal or other combination could enhance the performance, for instance using Rh-doped BaTiO₃ [35] or semiconductors such as InP:Fe [45] or CdTe [18]. Using this arrangement, we obtain a final output beam which is stable, suppressed and provides IR radiation which can be detected when the signal beam changes. This system forms the photorefractive adaptive interferometer arranged for IR OTD. In order to provide temporal variations with precise phase change, the signal beam is reflected with a high-reflector (HR) piezo mirror (PZT) which is connected to a high-voltage amplifier and a function generator.

The final part of the experimental setup includes the up-conversion stage. The frequency doubling of the laser is achieved in a single pass through a nonlinear crystal (C3), a BiB₃O₆ (BIBO) second-order crystal (aperture $3.91 \times 4.45 \text{ mm}^2$, length 2.82 mm). The crystal is cut for collinear critical type I ($e + e \rightarrow o$) interaction in the yz plane ($\phi = 90^\circ$) at an internal angle of ($\theta \cong 152^\circ$) at normal incidence. This geometry yields a maximum theoretical effective nonlinear coefficient of $d_{\text{eff}} \cong 3.3 \text{ pm/V}$ [46,47]. The output signal from the photorefractive system is focused onto the BIBO crystal with a lens, L3 ($f' = 50 \text{ mm}$). The IR and second harmonic beams are split by means of a harmonic separator (HS). The up-converted beam is focused by lens, L4 ($f' = 50 \text{ mm}$) onto a visible GaP photodetector (D1), Thorlabs DET25K/M (150-550 nm, 55 ns rise time, 4.8 mm^2). We must highlight that combination of femtosecond pulses with the BIBO crystal enables up-conversion by SHG in a simple single-pass scheme, even with the weak output average powers ($\leq 1 \text{ mW}$) from the photorefractive OTD. BIBO was chosen over other nonlinear crystals because of its higher d_{eff} . On the other hand, we use a second InGaAs photodetector (D2), a Thorlabs DET10C/M (700-1800 nm, 10 ns rise time, 0.8 mm^2) for the IR radiation. We deploy these two detectors to clearly separate the input-output detection wavelength ranges. Obviously, this work opens up the possibility to be extended to longer input wavelength, in which Si-based detectors are not possible, and detecting the up-converted output light with fast Si-based detectors.

4. Experimental procedure

As the first step, the experimental procedure involves enforcement of the photorefractive adaptive interferometer into a suppression state. To achieve that, we perform TWM in the two photorefractive crystals in tandem so as to obtain a significant level of background suppression and stability to perturbations. More precisely, we mix both signal and pump on the first photorefractive crystal, and, then we reuse the undepleted pump to perform TWM in the second crystal. As we explained in Section 2, we have to use delay-lines to synchronously pump photorefractive crystals, where the synchronization range for our mode-locked pulses is about $30 \mu\text{m}$, which is approximately the spatial length of the pulse. Therefore, we monitor the output light on both photodetectors and scan the pump delay line until we observe the onset of suppression. At that point, we leave the system evolving while the first photorefractive grating is created. Small adjustments of crystals orientations and realignment of pump beams and the delay line for spatial and temporal overlap are required in an iterative process to enhance the level of suppression. The procedure is repeated for the interaction on the second photorefractive crystal, scanning the signal delay line, in order to obtain further suppression. The IR output power of the OTD system for 100 mW input power is about 20 mW without pump and it drops down to 5 mW when pumped at 500 mW. Regarding the up-conversion process, the BIBO crystal is cut to operate around normal incidence. After focusing the IR beam, we scan the BIBO crystal position and angle to achieve SHG signal which can be detected. In this work, we present, for the first time, implementation and use of femtosecond pulses in the infrared for OTD in combination with a nonlinear crystal-based up-conversion for detection. Figure 2 shows examples of output

suppression in the IR and the corresponding up-converted signal using femtosecond pulses in the BIBO crystal. In the procedure, we pump only the first photorefractive crystal (SBN) and we find a very slow grating formation with about 50% SHG signal reduction after almost 1 minute. We then release the pump for the second photorefractive crystal (BaTiO₃) and the new grating is rapidly created, in about 200 ms, providing a final suppression state with an 80% SHG signal reduction.

Fig. 2. Example of femtosecond TWM grating formation for energy suppression. Intensity for IR beam at 805 nm (red) and for the up-converted beam by SHG (blue). Both curves include the initial intensity level, the background detection, the first crystal (SBN) suppression and the final suppression, when contribution of the second crystal (BaTiO₃) is added. The input signal and pump powers are 134 mW and 543 mW, respectively. Note that IR detector background has been offset by 1 V for better visualization. Oscilloscope acquisition is set at 500 S/s for 100 K points.

Additionally, the experimental procedure to demonstrate signal phase detection consists of applying different signal phase variations on the IR input signal and analyzing intensity outputs for both channels: IR and SHG in the blue. As shown in the experimental setup (see Fig. 1) the signal beam is reflected onto a HR mirror mounted on PZT, and a function generator in set to provide a collection of square pulses with different amplitudes, giving rise to different phase variations on the IR optical beam. In next section, we present main results making use of the described experimental procedures.

5. Results

We define the suppression contrast as the ratio of the signal output intensities with and without TWM, namely

$$\gamma^{\text{supp}} = (I^{\text{free}} - I^0) / I^{\text{free}}, \quad (4)$$

where I^{free} is signal intensity directly transmitted by the photorefractive crystal without TWM and we recall that $I^0 = \bar{I}_1^{\text{out}}$ is the corresponding background intensity for the reference suppression state (with TWM), as introduced in Sec. 2. Perfect suppression ($I^0 = 0$) means $\gamma^{\text{supp}} = 100\%$. Similarly, we define the intensity contrast for the OTD signal as

$$\gamma^{\text{OTD}} = I^{\text{OTD}} / I^0, \quad (5)$$

where I^{OTD} is the OTD signal defined in Eq. (2), that is the difference between the measured intensity and the background. Note that γ^{OTD} is a form of signal-to-noise ratio.

First, we measure the performance of our experimental setup in terms of output signal suppression. Figure 3 presents the suppression ratios, $\gamma_{\text{IR}}^{\text{supp}}$ and $\gamma_{\text{SHG}}^{\text{supp}}$, described by Eq. (4), for IR as well as up-converted light, respectively, as a function of the average pump power. As one can see from the plot, the IR suppression ratio is nearly constant for pump powers above 100 mW, reaching to a maximum value of 60%. The photorefractive gain (of the pump beam) and the corresponding suppression of the signal beam depend on the pump-signal intensity ratio at the entrance of the crystal [1,7]. Large ratios improve signal suppression (or pump gain). Since the signal input power was set at 125 mW, using pumps below that level degrades the suppression, and we can see from the plot that the suppression decays significantly below 15%.

Fig. 3. Signal output suppression contrast, γ^{supp} , Eq. (4), for IR (squares) and SHG (circles) depending on average pump power. The input signal average power was 125 mW. Plots contain experimental values and dashed lines are guide to the eye.

Interestingly, $\gamma_{\text{SHG}}^{\text{supp}}$ shows an increasing trend, reaching higher values than the IR. This behavior is expected from the quadratic dependence between fundamental and SHG. However, the suppression ratio keeps increasing slightly for pump powers above 400 mW, whereas the IR remains almost constant. We conclude that there is some beam change affecting the SHG process when IR pump power on photorefractive crystals increases, providing an additional decrease in the signal background. Notably, for the up-converted output signal, a suppression value as high as 80% is achieved.

Figure 4 displays the measured OTD output signals for an input signal with phase variations which are set by applying variable peak voltages to the PZT mirror in the form of electronic signal pulses (50 ms pulse duration, 0.5 Hz repetition rate, 5 ns rise time) which are short as compared to the response time of our photorefractive adaptive interferometer (200 ms). Certainly, our setup simultaneously uses two different photorefractive crystals with two different photorefractive response times, and the crystal that limits the OTD technique is the faster one, hence the 200 ms. If a change lasts longer, the faster crystal adapts to the new situation and the OTD premise is broken. Note that each electronic pulse affects some 3.8×10^6 mode-locked laser pulses, since the pulse period is 13 ns. As it can be seen, the output remains in a stable suppression state. As soon as the phase pulse is applied on the input IR beam, the output shows a clear signal in intensity and with significant contrast. After the pulse, the adaptive interferometer output reverts to the steady state. In more detail, Fig. 5 shows a zoom of a single pulse, showing similar performance between the IR and up-converted transient detection. The measured FWHM pulse

durations for IR and blue are 51 ± 1 ms and 49 ± 1 ms, respectively. However, we can see that the IR pulse has a small tail on the trailing edge and, thus, the final zero point of the pulse trace is shifted by about 8 ms with respect to the blue one. This means that the up-converted OTD signal, which involves the SHG process as well as the GaP detector, exhibits slightly better symmetrical shape and faster recovery to steady state.

Fig. 4. Transient output signal of a train of IR input signal pulses with π phase variation, detected by the IR photodetector (red signal) as well as the visible detector (blue signal) after up-conversion by SHG. Note that IR detector background has been offset by 1 V for better visualization. Oscilloscope acquisition is set at 100 kS/s for 100 K points.

Fig. 5. Transient output signal of a single IR input signal pulse with π phase variation, detected by the IR photodetector (red signal) as well as the visible detector (blue signal) after up-conversion by SHG. Note that IR detector background has been offset by 1 V for better visualization. Oscilloscope acquisition is set at 250 kS/s for 100 K points.

In order to characterize the performance of our system for phase measurements, we arrange a set of intensity measurements for different values of phase change applied on the IR signal

beam. Figure 6 displays the measured OTD output signals for input signals with phase variations ranging from 0 to π . As can be seen, both the IR detector and the visible detector can clearly distinguish phase changes even down to 0.5 rad. The IR intensity is an excellent fit to Eq. (3). On the other hand, we find that the best fit to the measured up-converted intensity is a quadratic function of the IR transient output, in which a linear contribution is also present. This behavior has been observed in similar SHG experiments in BIBO [47] for low pump powers as in our experiment.

Fig. 6. IR (top) and SHG (bottom) transient output signals corresponding to applied IR signal-phase change. Plots contain experimental mean values (squares and circles) where background levels I^0 of 300 mW and 2.7 mW for IR and SHG, respectively, have been subtracted according to the definition of I^{OTD} in Eq. (2). The solid line in (top) is a fit to Eq. (3), $a_1 \sin^2(\Delta\varphi_1/2)$, with $a_1 = 1827 \pm 7$ and $R^2 = 0.997$. The solid line in (bottom) is a fit to $a_2 \sin^2(\Delta\varphi_1/2) + [a_3 \sin^2(\Delta\varphi_1/2)]^2$, with $a_2 = 2.386 \pm 1.353$, $a_3 = 2.156 \pm 0.360$, and $R^2 = 0.994$.

Moreover, Fig. 7 shows the intensity contrast for the OTD signals, γ_{IR}^{OTD} and γ_{SHG}^{OTD} , Eq. (5), for both the IR and up-converted signals. The maximum contrast in the IR is higher than 600%, and the contrast for a signal-phase change of only 0.5 rad is $\sim 50\%$. For the up-converted beam we find that the maximum contrast is about 250%, very significant in spite of the significant reduction of intensity on the visible detector. Moreover, a contrast of 10% is still obtained for the IR signal-phase change of 0.5 rad.

Interestingly, the parametric dependence between IR and visible detected intensities, as shown in Fig. 8, has a good fit to a quadratic function.

We need to point out that our system is operating in suppression mode for transient detection and, therefore, the output intensities are relatively low, of the order of few mW. As such, the attainment of up-conversion is challenging, but we demonstrate the practical realization thanks to the use of ultrashort femtosecond pulses and the BIBO crystal. The intensities of the up-converted light into the visible are also weak, below the mW level, and thus, we are in a working range that could be approximated by linear-type with low conversion efficiencies. From our experimental data, the trend towards the quadratic dependence starts to be present with further increase in input power. As we already point out, these results are compatible with the SHG studies of efficiency that has been performed on BIBO crystals with femtosecond pulses [47], where conversion efficiencies are very low ($<10\%$) for fundamental powers below 100 mW.

Fig. 7. OTD contrast, γ^{OTD} , Eq. (5), depending on the signal-phase change, for the transient output intensity detected in the IR (squares) and visible (circles) after up-conversion by SHG. Dashed lines are a guide for the eye.

Fig. 8. Parametric plot between the IR and SHG intensity contrast, $\gamma_{\text{IR}}^{\text{OTD}}$ and $\gamma_{\text{SHG}}^{\text{OTD}}$, Eq. (5). The best fit of experimental data seems to be a quadratic function, $\gamma_{\text{SHG}}^{\text{OTD}} = b_1(\gamma_{\text{IR}}^{\text{OTD}})^2 + b_2\gamma_{\text{IR}}^{\text{OTD}} + b_3$, where $b_1 = 4.132 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $b_2 = 0.1538$, $b_3 = 4.187$, and a correlation factor $R^2 = 0.997$.

Finally, to demonstrate additional merits of the up-converted light for the OTD system, we deliberately added a small cw component to the mode-locked pulses, by adjusting the slit responsible for Kerr-lens mode-locking inside the Ti:sapphire laser cavity.

Figure 9 shows the effect of cw contribution, giving rise to a noisy laser output with some significant intensity fluctuations on the IR detector. The mean values of the IR output and detector background with their standard deviations (*std*) are 1433 ± 26 mV and 1000 ± 8 mV, respectively. Nevertheless, the output in the visible remains stable, with a mean value given by 3.4 ± 0.3 mV and a detector background at 0 mV with same *std*. Therefore, thanks to the up-conversion process, which converts the femtosecond pulses from IR into the blue, but not the remaining cw component fluctuations, the SHG detector only generates a transient output signal when a phase change is applied to the input beam.

Fig. 9. Example of the effect of continuous-wave variations on OTD with mode-locked pulses. Transient output signal detected by the IR photodetector (red signal) as well as the visible detector (blue signal) after up-conversion by SHG. The recording includes also the level for the detector's background and a controlled phase change applied by a squared signal with $\pi/2$ phase variation. Note that IR detector background has been offset by 1 V for better visualization. Oscilloscope acquisition is set at 10 kS/s for 100 K points.

6. Conclusion

We have experimentally demonstrated, for the first time to our knowledge, the implementation of a photorefractive TWM using IR femtosecond pulses for background suppression and detection of transient optical phases in a photodetector.

We have confirmed the relation between input and output phases for the entire range from 0 to π applied to the IR beam, in agreement with squared-sinusoidal type theoretical dependence defined by Eq. (3). Furthermore, we have demonstrated up-conversion of the transient output pulses combining femtosecond pulses with a suitable nonlinear crystal (BIBO) for SHG. We have obtained a quadratic-like relation between IR and SHG transient output intensities for the IR signal-phase changes within the range 0 to π . This result indicates that even in the presence of low output powers, in the mW level, the SHG process for the transient detection is still possible. Moreover, the up-converted transient detection is not sensitive to cw contributions to the mode-locked pulses, which makes the technique robust against fluctuations with only mode-locked pulses synchronized for two-wave mixing providing transient signals on the visible detector.

The described up-conversion method provides further background suppression with phase sensitivity using detection in the visible range, which is especially important for low-power

small-phase change signals, and thus demonstrates its potential application as a sensor. Moreover, the demonstrated possibility of up-conversion into the visible could be extended to imaging, where CCD devices provide faster response with higher resolution.

It is worthwhile to highlight that the described technique allows the use of photorefractive materials pumped in the IR, which can be faster, such as photorefractive semiconductors, allowing detection in shorter wavelengths. On the other hand, the concept may also be applied to input beams by up-converting the pump and the input signal after passing the sample, which could be at longer wavelengths such as mid-IR, thus enabling TWM for OTD in a photorefractive material suitable for the up-converted laser wavelength, for instance.

Finally, we believe that this approach opens up new possibilities by exploiting unsurpassed wavelength flexibility for both sampling and detection, which allows exploitation of different laser wavelengths for OTD and its applications in both single-spot detection as well as imaging.

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Data Availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

References

1. P. Yeh, *Introduction to Photorefractive Nonlinear Optics* (Wiley, 1993).
2. N. V. Kukhtarev, V. B. Markov, S. G. Odulov, M. S. Soskin, and V. L. Vinetskii, "Holographic storage in electrooptic crystals.1. Steady-state," *Ferroelectrics* **22**(1), 949–960 (1979).
3. N. V. Kukhtarev, V. B. Markov, S. G. Odulov, M. S. Soskin, and V. L. Vinetskii, "Holographic storage in electrooptic crystals.2. Beam coupling-light amplification," *Ferroelectrics* **22**(1), 961–964 (1979).
4. I. Rossomakhin and S. Stepanov, "Linear adaptive interferometers via diffusion recording in cubic photorefractive crystals," *Opt. Commun.* **86**(2), 199–204 (1991).
5. A. A. Kamshilin, R. V. Romashko, and Y. N. Kulchin, "Adaptive interferometry with photorefractive crystals," *J. Appl. Phys.* **105**(3), 031101 (2009).
6. M. Cronin-Golomb, A. M. Biernacki, C. Lin, and H. Kong, "Photorefractive time differentiation of coherent optical-images," *Opt. Lett.* **12**(12), 1029–1031 (1987).
7. D. Z. Anderson and J. Feinberg, "Optical novelty filters," *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* **25**(3), 635–647 (1989).
8. R. S. Cudney, R. M. Pierce, and J. Feinberg, "The transient detection microscope," *Nature* **332**(6163), 424–426 (1988).
9. M. Woerdemann, F. Holtmann, and C. Denz, "Full-field particle velocimetry with a photorefractive optical novelty filter," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **93**(2), 021108 (2008).
10. F. Holtmann, M. Oevermann, and C. Denz, "Dynamic phase-contrast stereoscopy for microflow velocimetry," *Appl. Phys. B* **95**(3), 633–636 (2009).
11. M. Sedlatschek, J. Trumpfheller, J. Hartmann, M. Müller, C. Denz, and T. Tschudi, "Differentiation and subtraction of amplitude and phase images using a photorefractive novelty filter," *Appl. Phys. B* **68**(5), 1047–1054 (1999).
12. V. V. Krishnamachari and C. Denz, "Real-time phase measurement with a photorefractive novelty filter microscope," *J. Opt. A: Pure Appl. Opt.* **5**(5), S239–S243 (2003).
13. V. V. Krishnamachari, O. Grothe, H. Deitmar, and C. Denz, "Novelty filtering with a photorefractive lithium-niobate crystal," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **87**(7), 071105 (2005).
14. A. Esteban-Martín, J. García-Monreal, F. Silva, and G. J. de Valcárcel, "Interferometric measurement of complex-field changes in transient detection imaging," *Opt. Express* **28**(20), 28782–28791 (2020).
15. S. A. Diddams, L. Hollberg, and V. Mbele, "Molecular fingerprinting with the resolved modes of a femtosecond laser frequency comb," *Nature* **445**(7128), 627–630 (2007).
16. J. M. Ingram and A. W. Fountain III, "Development of a thermal evaporation cell for gas-phase infrared absorption spectroscopy of compounds with low volatility," *Appl. Spectrosc.* **61**(11), 1254–1258 (2007).
17. L. Peng, P. Yu, D. D. Nolte, and M. R. Melloch, "High-speed adaptive interferometer for optical coherence-domain reflectometry through turbid media," *Opt. Lett.* **28**(6), 396–398 (2003).
18. K. Shcherbin and M. B. Klein, "Adaptive interferometers with no external field using reflection gratings in CdTe:Ge at 1550 nm," *Opt. Commun.* **282**(13), 2580–2585 (2009).

19. M. B. Klein, "Beam coupling in undoped GaAs at 1.06 μm using the photorefractive effect," *Opt. Lett.* **9**(8), 350–352 (1984).
20. P. Delaye, A. Blouin, D. Drolet, L. A. de Montmorillon, G. Roosen, and J. P. Monchalín, "Detection of ultrasonic motion of a scattering surface by photorefractive InP:Fe under an applied dc field," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **14**(7), 1723–1734 (1997).
21. F. M. Davidson and L. Boutsikaris, "Homodyne detection using photorefractive materials as beamsplitters," *Opt. Eng.* **29**(4), 369–377 (1990).
22. A. Blouin and J.-P. Monchalín, "Detection of ultrasonic motion of a scattering surface by two-wave mixing in a photorefractive GaAs crystal," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **65**(8), 932–934 (1994).
23. R. K. Ing and J.P. Monchalín, "Broad-band optical-detection of ultrasound by 2-wave mixing in a photorefractive crystal," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **59**(25), 3233–3235 (1991).
24. L. A. de Montmorillon, Ph. Delaye, and G. Roosen, "Photorefractive interferometer for ultrasound detection," in: K. Kuroda, ed., *Progress in Photorefractive Nonlinear Optics* (Taylor & Francis, London, 2002).
25. L. Peng, M. M. Varma, W. Cho, F. E. Regnier, and D. D. Nolte, "Adaptive interferometry of protein on a BioCD," *Appl. Opt.* **46**(22), 5384–5395 (2007).
26. A. J. Torregrosa, E. Karamehmedovic, H. Maestre, M. L. Rico, and J. Capmany, "Up-Conversion sensing of 2D spatially-modulated infrared information-carrying beams with Si-based cameras," *Sensors* **20**(12), 3610 (2020).
27. A.S. Ashik, Callum F. O'Donnell, S. Chaitanya Kumar, M. Ebrahim-Zadeh, P. Tidemand-Lichtenberg, and C. Pedersen, "Mid-infrared upconversion imaging using femtosecond pulses," *Photonics Res.* **7**(7), 783–791 (2019).
28. S. Junaid, S. Chaitanya Kumar, M. Mathez, M. Hermes, N. Stone, N. Shepherd, M. Ebrahim-Zadeh, P. Tidemand-Lichtenberg, and C. Pedersen, "Video-rate, mid-infrared hyperspectral upconversion imaging," *Optica* **6**(6), 702–708 (2019).
29. X.-H. Chen, X.-F. Han, and Y.-X. Weng, "Transient spectrometer for near-IR fluorescence based on parametric frequency upconversion," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **89**(6), 061127 (2006).
30. S. Cao, H. Li, Z. Zhao, S. Zhang, J. Chen, J. Xu, J. R. Knutson, and L. Brand, "Ultrafast fluorescence spectroscopy via upconversion and its applications in biophysics," *Molecules* **26**(1), 211 (2021).
31. Md. Masudul Kabir, D. Ito, Y. Oishi, and F. Kannari, "Two-wave mixing amplification of femtosecond laser pulses at 800 nm in Rh:BaTiO₃ photorefractive crystal," *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **50**(10R), 102702 (2011).
32. L. H. Acioli, M. Ulman, E. P. Ippen, J. G. Fujimoto, H. Kong, B. S. Chen, and M. Cronin-Golomb, "Femtosecond temporal encoding in barium titanate," *Opt. Lett.* **16**(24), 1984–1986 (1991).
33. X. S. Yao, V. Dominic, and J. Feinberg, "Theory of beam coupling and pulse shaping of mode-locked laser pulses in a photorefractive crystal," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **7**(12), 2347–2355 (1990).
34. M. Horowitz, B. Fischer, Y. Barad, and Y. Silberberg, "Photorefractive effect in a BaTiO₃ crystal at the 1.5- μm wavelength regime by two-photon absorption," *Opt. Lett.* **21**(15), 1120–1122 (1996).
35. B. A. Wechsler, M. B. Klein, C. C. Nelson, and R. N. Schwartz, "Spectroscopic and photorefractive properties of infrared-sensitive rhodium-doped barium titanate," *Opt. Lett.* **19**(8), 536–538 (1994).
36. V. Dominic, X. S. Yao, R. M. Pierce, and J. Feinberg, "Measuring the coherence length of mode-locked laser pulses in real time," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **56**(6), 521–523 (1990).
37. A. Shumelyuk, M. Imlau, V. Dieckmann, H. Badorreck, A. Grabar, and S. Odoulov, "Self-diffraction from two-photon absorption gratings in Sn₂P₂S₆," *Opt. Lett.* **37**(19), 4065–4067 (2012).
38. G. Montemezzani, C. Medrano, P. Günter, and M. Zgonik, "Charge carrier photoexcitation and two-wave mixing in dichroic materials," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **79**(18), 3403–3406 (1997).
39. K. Jarasiunas, J. Vaitkus, P. Delaye, and G. Roosen, "Dislocation density-dependent photorefractive effect in (001)-cut GaAs," *Opt. Lett.* **19**(23), 1946–1948 (1994).
40. G. C. Valley, "Short-pulse grating formation in photorefractive materials," *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* **19**(11), 1637–1645 (1983).
41. H. Okamura, K. Takeuchi, T. Tanaka, and K. Kuroda, "Grating formation with very short pulses in photorefractive materials: weak excitation limit," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **14**(10), 2650–2656 (1997).
42. A. L. Smirl, G. C. Valley, R. A. Mullen, K. Bohnert, C. D. Mire, and T. F. Boggess, "Picosecond photorefractive effect in BaTiO₃," *Opt. Lett.* **12**(7), 501–503 (1987).
43. K. Buse, A. Gerwens, S. Wevering, and E. Krätzig, "Charge-transport parameters of photorefractive strontium-barium niobate crystals doped with cerium," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **15**(6), 1674–1677 (1998).
44. X. Yao and J. Feinberg, "Photorefractive pulse coupling in the frequency domain," *Opt. Lett.* **18**(2), 104–106 (1993).
45. N. Khelifaoui, D. Wolfersberger, G. Kugel, N. Fressengeas, and M. Chauvet, "Temporal behavior of two-wave-mixing in photorefractive InP:Fe versus temperature," *Opt. Commun.* **261**(1), 169–174 (2006).
46. M. Ghotbi, A. Esteban-Martin, and M. Ebrahim-Zadeh, "BiB₃O₆ femtosecond optical parametric oscillator," *Opt. Lett.* **31**(21), 3128–3130 (2006).
47. M. Ghotbi and M. Ebrahim-Zadeh, "Optical second harmonic generation properties of BiB₃O₆," *Opt. Express* **12**(24), 6002–6019 (2004).